

Analytical Applications of 2-Hydroxy-3-Chloro-5-Methylpropio-phenone Oxime (HCMPO): Gravimetric Determination of Copper, Nickel and Cobalt

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2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methylpropio-phenone oxime (HCMPO) has been found to be a wide spectrum precipitant for a number of transition metal ions. It gives a buff coloured bis-chelate (pH 3.0-8.0) with Cu^{2+} , a light green bis-chelate (pH 5.0-10.0) with Ni^{2+} and a yellow bis-chelate (pH 6.5-8.0) with Co^{2+} . The bis-chelates are granular and quantitative. Copper, nickel and cobalt have been determined gravimetrically in their binary or ternary mixtures.

2-HYDROXY-3-c h l o r o-5-methylpropio-phenone oxime (HCMPO) has the system $\begin{array}{c} \text{---}\text{C}=\text{C---} \\ | \\ \text{OH} \end{array}$

= NOH- similar to many precipitating agents for a number of transition metal ions. The investigation of reagents having such system has been undertaken by several workers¹⁻³. The studies on salicylal-doxime²⁻⁴, resacetophenone oxime^{5,6} and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime⁷ lead to the conclusion that the precipitation is a function of pH and characteristic of the reagent. Salicylal-doxime and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime complexes of copper are somewhat soluble in ethanol. Therefore, excess of the reagent which gets precipitated is difficult to wash out completely. HCMPO has some advantages over these reagents. The copper and nickel complexes are insoluble in 60% ethanol and excess of the reagent which precipitates can be easily washed out by this solvent. The reagent has been found to precipitate Co^{2+} quantitatively and hence it can be used to determine Co^{2+} . Gravimetric determination of copper, nickel and cobalt in their binary or ternary mixtures has been carried out with satisfactory results taking advantage of the different pH range for precipitation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. Grade. Stock solutions of metal ions prepared by dissolving pure salts, in double distilled water, were employed after standardisation by standard methods. 0.05 M solution of cations was used in most cases and the pH was adjusted to a known value using acetic acid and buffer solutions.

Reagent : 2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methylpropio-phenone oxime (HCMPO) :

HCMP⁸ was obtained in almost quantitative yield by the Fries migration of 2-chloro-*p*-cresyl propionate

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in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Its oxime was prepared by the reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate in dilute alcohol. It was further purified by repeated crystallisations from ethanol, m.p. 205°.

Analysis :

Found : N, 6.4; Cl, 16.3%. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$ requires : N, 6.6; Cl, 16.6%.

Determination of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} in their binary mixtures :

A solution containing a known amount of two cations was taken in a 400 ml pyrex beaker, diluted to 200 ml and the pH was adjusted to a required value using acetic acid and ammonia buffer in case of copper and nickel. The solution was warmed to 60°-70° and an ethanolic solution of HCMPO (1%) was added dropwise with constant stirring until no precipitation took place on adding excess of the reagent solution. The complex was digested on a water bath for 30 min. It was filtered while hot through a sintered glass crucible (G-4). The complex was washed with hot water (60°-70°) to remove foreign ions. It was finally washed with 60% ethanol. The complex was dried at 110°-140° to a constant weight and weighed as $M(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl})_2$, $M = \text{Cu}^{2+}$ or Ni^{2+} .

The filtrate and washings after the removal of the first cation complex were collected for the estimation of the second cation. The solution was warmed upto 60° and the pH of the solution was raised to the required value using acetic acid and ammonia buffer in case of nickel and acetate borax in case of cobalt. The experimental procedure for precipitation and estimation of second cation⁺ was the same as described in the case of first cation. The complex was dried at 110°-140° to a constant weight and weighed as $M(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl})_2$, $M = \text{Ni}^{2+}$ or Co^{2+} . The results are given in table 1.

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} AND Co^{2+} IN THEIR BINARY MIXTURES

Wt. of metal ion in mg.	pH	Wt. of complex in mg.	Metal ion found in complex in mg.	Error in mg.
(i) Cu^{2+} 31.4	3.0	244.0	31.5	+0.1
Ni^{2+} 30.4	5.5	250.0	30.3	-0.1
(ii) Cu^{2+} 31.4	3.0	242.0	31.2	-0.2
Co^{2+} 29.2	7.5	238.0	29.0	-0.2
(iii) Ni^{2+} 30.4	5.5	251.0	30.5	+0.1
Co^{2+} 29.2	7.5	238.0	29.0	-0.2

+ Cobalt complex was washed with 20% ethanol.

Determination of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} when present in the same solution :

A solution containing a known amount of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} was taken in 400 ml. pyrex glass beaker and diluted to about 150 ml. and pH was adjusted to 3.0. The solution was warmed upto 60° and excess of the reagent solution was added. Copper complex precipitated was digested, filtered and estimated as before.

The filtrate and washings after removal of the copper complex were collected for the estimation of nickel. The solution was concentrated to about 150 ml., warmed upto 60° and the pH was raised to 5.5. The reagent solution was added in excess. Nickel precipitated was estimated as before.

The filtrate along with washings after removal of the nickel complex, was collected for the estimation of cobalt. The solution was warmed upto 60° and the pH was raised to 7.5. Cobalt was precipitated. However, excess of the reagent was added to complete the precipitation of cobalt. The precipitate was digested, filtered, washed and dried as in the previous case. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2. DETERMINATION OF Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} AND Co^{2+} IN THE SAME SOLUTION

Wt. of metal ion in mg.	pH	Wt. of complex in mg.	Metal ion found in complex in mg.	Error in mg.
Cu^{2+} 15.7	3.0	120.0	15.5	-0.2
Ni^{2+} 15.2	5.5	124.0	15.1	-0.1
Co^{2+} 14.5	7.5	121.0	14.7	+0.1

Composition of the complexes of Copper, Nickel and Cobalt :

The composition of complexes as determined by analysis is suggested in parallel to those of salicylal-doxime⁸ and *o*-hydroxy ketoximes⁷.

$M = \text{Cu}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{or } \text{Co}^{2+}$.

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